

Data Management Plan Information

Classes of errors in DOI names (Revised Version of Data Management Plan)

The data involved in this project are used to answer the following research questions: what are the classes of errors that characterize invalid DOIs? Which classes of errors can be addressed through automatic processes so as to get the correct DOIs? How many correct DOIs and, consequently, citations have been obtained by applying such automatic processing? While searching for answers to these questions, we used DOI names that have been collected by the OpenCitations Index Of Crossref Open DOI-To-DOI References (COCI) while processing data provided by Crossref.

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Organisations

Alma Mater Studiorum, Università di Bologna

Researchers

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Datasets

Title: Classes of errors in DOI names: code

Template: Horizon 2020

External References

Data Repositories

External Datasets

Registries

Services

This dataset contains the source code used to clean a CSV list of invalid DOI names and to output the correct ones, the classes of errors, and the ones that were not possible to fix automatically. The data we process is an example of DOI names found in Crossref. In particular, four classes of errors are addressed: previously invalid DOIs become valid, prefix errors, suffix errors, and other type errors.

Dataset Description

1 Data Summary

1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

[To develop a product, To improve a product]

Comment: Our purpose is to correcting errors in DOI names. In doing so, we used the CSV file where valid and invalid citations were collected. This DOI names collected by COCI project from Crossref open citations.

1.2 What types of data will the project generate/collect?

[Other]

Source code

1.3 What formats of data will the project generate/collect?

[Software - Java, C, Python]

Python-based software for cleaning CSV files with invalid DOIs.

1.4 What is the origin of the data?

[Primary data]

1.5 What is the expected size of the data?

KB (kilobyte)

Comment: The scale of Python scripts used to address these types of problems is usually calculated in KB.

1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

[Researchers, Other]

Stakeholders in the Scholarly domain, involved in the collection and reuse of DOIs from secondary sources.

2 Reusable Data

2.1 Will you re-use any existing data and how?

Yes

Peroni, S. (2021). Citations to invalid DOI-identified entities obtained from processing DOI-to-DOI citations to add in COCI (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.4625300>

[To compare and combine with other data, To develop new products/ services]

2.2 Where do the data reside?

2.3 Which data will be re-used?

3 FAIR Data

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

Our descriptive metadata will describe a resource for purposes such as discovery and identification. It will include elements such as title, abstract, author, and keywords.

3.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

Datacite

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

3.1.4 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

<http://purl.org/spar/datacite>

3.1.5 Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

Comment: Codes and metadata are kept in online and free of charge. This is one of the highlights of our open science work. It has been developed in accordance with FAIR principles.

3.1.6 Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

Comment: : All of our data is stored, including metadata that describes our research data, to validate the results presented in scientific publications.

3.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

3.1.8 Please provide more details and examples on used naming conversions

<https://www.python.org/dev/peps/pep-0008/>

PEP 8

3.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

3.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for your data?

Yes

Comment: We will use The Digital Object Identifier (DOI®) System is a managed system for persistent identification of content on digital networks.

3.1.11 Persistent identifiers

DOI

3.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for your data?

No

Comment: We are not providing searchable metadata. To do so, we need to organized them in a graph in a uri, but we are not doing this.

3.1.15 Will you use standardised formats for your data?

Yes

Jupyter Python Notebook, Python Compiled File, CSV Schema, Comma Separated Values

3.1.18 Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Comment: All file formats are free and enable to re-use. We build free python code that can be reused by anyone.

3.1.20 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

3.1.22 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

Yes

Comment: Our metadata for a document might include a collection of information like the author, file size, the date the document was created, and keywords to describe the document.

3.2 Making data openly accessible

3.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the data?

No

3.2.2 Will your data be openly accessible?

all

3.2.4 How will the data be made available?

[Repository of Archive]

Zenodo, GitHub

3.2.6 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

secure with backup and recovery

Comment: We will have keeping 4 copies of our data for each member. We are verifying our access periodically.

3.2.7 Are there any methods or tools required to access the data?

No

We use catch-all repository Zenodo, maintained by CERN.

3.2.10 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

at end of project

Comment: While conducting our research, some articles about the codes developed attracted our attention, we are ready to share them

3.3 Making data interoperable

3.3.1 Will you use a controlled vocabulary for your data?

No

3.3.2 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.4 Increase data reuse

3.4.1 When do you plan to make your data available for reuse?

immediately

3.4.4 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your data?

ISC License

3.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of your data?

No

3.4.8 Will you provide any support for data reuse?

Yes

Comment: Zenodo

3.4.9 How long do you intend to support data reuse?

More than 10 years

4 Allocation of resources

4.1 How will the cost of making your data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

[Other]

4.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage your data, if not who will be responsible for the management of your data?

No

Comment: The whole research team is responsible of the data management.

4.3 Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the project data

Comment: Cristian Santini (orcid:0000-0001-7363-6737), Ricarda Boente (orcid:0000-0002-2133-8735), Arcangelo Massari (orcid:0000-0002-8420-0696), Deniz Tural (orcid:0000-0002-6391-4198). All group members are equally reasonably responsible for the management of the data. Everyone is responsible for the codes developed to clear data management plan, workflow, DOI names error classes.

4.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

[Other]

5 Data Security

5.1 What do you plan to do with research data of limited use?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

6 Ethical aspects

6.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

6.2 What are the methods used for processing sensitive/personal data?

[Not available]

7 Other

7.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Comment: Researchers and trustworthy repositories are partners in Open and FAIR data

Title: Classes of errors in DOI names: output dataset

Template: Horizon 2020

External References

Data Repositories

External Datasets

Registries

Services

The output dataset consists of a CSV file reporting the classes of errors associated with various DOI names, the correct ones, and the ones that were not possible to fix automatically. We used DOI names that have been collected by the OpenCitations Index Of Crossref Open DOI-To-DOI References (COCI) while processing data provided by Crossref.

Dataset Description

1 Data Summary

1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

[To obtain information, To improve a product, To combine with other data]

Comment: The data collected is intended to obtain which DOI names extracted from Crossref are found to be invalid, in order to produce a new dataset that contains the correct data. To do so, it is necessary to combine existing data with other data obtained through the DOI and Crossref APIs.

1.2 What types of data will the project generate/collect?

[sample or specimen data]

The processed data is a sample of DOI names present in Crossref that were found to be invalid.

1.3 What formats of data will the project generate/collect?

[Text files - MS Word docs, .txt files, PDF, RTF, XML (Extensible Markup Language), Other]

COCI obtain the information for this project in the form of a CSV file containing pairs of correct citing DOIs and invalid citing DOIs.

1.4 What is the origin of the data?

[Secondary data]

1.5 What is the expected size of the data?

MB (megabyte)

Comment: An output of about 70 MB is expected, since the input weighs 60 MB, to which additional data that will be the result of the processing will be added.

1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

[Researchers, Research communities, Education, Industry]

This work is especially useful in the area of Scientometrics. Therefore, it is especially aimed at the world of research and the scientific community, as well as the related publishing industry.

2 Reusable Data

2.1 Will you re-use any existing data and how?

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[To compare and combine with other data, To develop new products/ services]

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3 FAIR Data

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Yes

Our descriptive metadata will describe a resource for purposes such as discovery and identification. It will include elements such as title, abstract, author, and keywords.

3.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

3.1.4 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

<http://purl.org/spar/datacite>

3.1.5 Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

Comment: Both data files and metadata are kept in online and free of charge. This is one of the highlights of our open science work. It has been developed in accordance with FAIR principles.

3.1.6 Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

Comment: : All of our data is stored, including metadata that describes our research data, to validate the results presented in scientific publications.

3.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

3.1.8 Please provide more details and examples on used naming conversions

3.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

No

3.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for your data?

Yes

Comment: We will use The Digital Object Identifier (DOI®) System is a managed system for persistent identification of content on digital networks.

3.1.11 Persistent identifiers

DOI

3.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for your data?

No

3.1.15 Will you use standardised formats for your data?

Yes

Python Compiled File, CSV Schema

3.1.18 Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Comment: Yes, file formats are free and enable to re-use.

3.1.20 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

3.1.22 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

Yes

Comment: Our metadata for a document might include a collection of information like the author, file size, the date the document was created, and keywords to describe the document.

3.2 Making data openly accessible

3.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the data?

No

3.2.2 Will your data be openly accessible?

all

3.2.4 How will the data be made available?

[Repository of Archive]

GitHub, Zenodo

3.2.6 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

secure with backup and recovery

Comment: We are storing our data in Github. Github platform is in charge for our storage sufficiently secure for the data. We are verifying our access periodically.

3.2.7 Are there any methods or tools required to access the data?

No

We use catch-all repository Zenodo, maintained by CERN.

3.2.10 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

at end of project

Comment: While conducting our research, there were some articles that attracted the attention of all members of the group. We are ready to share them.

3.3 Making data interoperable

3.3.1 Will you use a controlled vocabulary for your data?

No

3.3.2 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.4 Increase data reuse

3.4.1 When do you plan to make your data available for reuse?

immediately

3.4.4 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your data?

ISC License

3.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of your data?

No

3.4.8 Will you provide any support for data reuse?

Yes

Comment: Zenodo

3.4.9 How long do you intend to support data reuse?

More than 10 years

4 Allocation of resources

4.1 How will the cost of making your data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

[Other]

Comment: The entire workflow will involve the use of open source and free infrastructures, such as GitHub and Zenodo. S.

4.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage your data, if not who will be responsible for the management of your data?

No

Comment: The whole research team is responsible of the data management.

4.3 Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the project data

Comment: Cristian Santini (orcid:0000-0001-7363-6737), Ricarda Boente (orcid:0000-0002-2133-8735), Arcangelo Massari (orcid:0000-0002-8420-0696), Deniz Tural (orcid:0000-0002-6391-4198). All group members are equally reasonably responsible for the management of the data. Everyone is responsible for the codes developed to clear data management plan, workflow, DOI names error classes.

4.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

[Other]

5 Data Security

5.1 What do you plan to do with research data of limited use?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

6 Ethical aspects

6.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

6.2 What are the methods used for processing sensitive/personal data?
[Not available]

7 Other

7.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?
No

Comment: Researchers and trustworthy repositories are partners in Open and FAIR data.